

ETHNONYMS AND THEIR RESEARCH ISSUES IN KARAKALPAK LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: this article discusses the significance of onomastics within linguistics, specifically its sub-field ethnonymy, and its connections with other sciences. It also explores the research object of anthroponymics, its interdisciplinary study with sciences such as history, literature, ethnography, and sociology, and distinctive characteristics of anomastics.

Keywords: history, linguistics, ethnic layers, ethnonymy, tribe, nation, people, ethnogenetics.

In Karakalpak linguistics, while toponymy studies place names (geographical names), ethnonymy is a branch of onomastics that studies the origin and formation of peoples. In social-humanitarian sciences, the terms “ethnos” and “ethnic unity” are commonly used. The term “ethnos” is understood in both narrow and broad senses. For example, the term “people” can refer to the world’s population, the American people, the Russian people, the people of Uzbekistan, the people of Karakalpakstan, and even smaller groups of people within a region. An ethnic unity is considered a social association that emerged in specific circumstances during a natural-historical development process. In science, there are three types of ethnic unity stages: tribe, elat (a historical term for a tribal or ethnic group), and nation.

The names of tribes, community, people, nations are called ethnonyms in science. The term “ethnonym” is derived from the Greek words “ethnos” meaning “people” and “onyma” meaning “name, term” [1:10,18]. In ancient times, ethnonyms were used as battle cries, tribe names, and emblems. They were named after clans, tribes, communities, peoples, and nations, as well as tribe leaders, elders, and heroes, and were also used as place names (geographical names). Ethnonymics, which studies the history of the origin and formation of ethnonyms, is a branch of onomastics. Ethnonymics deals with issues such as collecting the names of clans, tribes, ethnic groups, nations, and other ethnic units in a particular language, their origin, the main motives for their naming, the vocabulary composition of the names, the role of substrate and

adstrate material in them, the meaning and etymology of ethnonyms, their formation, and the principles and rules for compiling ethnonymic dictionaries.

In linguistics, there are diverse opinions regarding the term “ethnonym”. A notable article on this topic is A.S. Polyakov’s “On the Question of the Content of the Concept “Ethnonym”.”

The article presents conflicting opinions and viewpoints of scholars on the term “ethnonym”: “A.A. Belsky’s definition of ethnonyms states that they are a type of coynonyms (coynonym - a common nickname for several authors - B.N.) belonging to anthroponyms. On the other hand, A.V. Superanskiy argues that ethnonyms are incorrectly included in the onomastic group and essentially considers them a type of lexical category” [2].

Ethnonymy is also closely related to toponymy. Some place names (geographical names), community settlements, and even cities are named after clans, tribes, or peoples. Conversely, some ethnonyms have originated from geographical place names. The origins and reasons for the formation of clan, tribal, and national names are deeply intertwined with the centuries-long history of the people. Therefore, ethnonyms play a crucial role in determining the ethnic composition and genesis of a population. Currently, ethnonyms are being studied in close connection with fields such as ethnonymy, history, ethnography, and linguistics. Looking at the research on ethnonyms, we observe that they have been comprehensively studied in both world linguistics and Turkic linguistics.

In world linguistics, specialists from the “Onomastics” group, established in 1967 at the N.N. Miklukho-Maklay Institute of Ethnography in Moscow, conducted specialized research on ethnonymy. Under the leadership of V.A. Nikonov, the group members published the first collection of articles on the issue of ethnonyms, titled “Ethnonyms” [3]. This collection featured articles prepared by twenty-seven scholars on ethnonymy. Following the publication of this collection, the study of ethnonyms has been undertaken, leading to the publication of numerous scientific works, monographs, and scholarly articles. Among such works, Professor A.I. Popov’s monograph “Names of the peoples of the USSR” [4] stands out. This work consists of two parts. The first part of the book discusses the ethnonyms of scythians, sarmatians, thracians, goths, huns, bulgars, khazars, avars, slavs, antes, dums, russians, and varyags. The second part provides a historical-etymological and linguistic analysis of ethnonyms such as esti, chud, krevins, kors, ves, karelian, saemi, yam, vod, lithuania, golyad, samogitian, merya, muroma, mordva, mari, udmurt, komi, burtas, pecheneg,

gorokhs, berendeys, chernye klobuki, polovtsian, ugar, kasog, as, alban, iber, mansi, khanty, nenets, enets, nganasan, and selkup.

In D.G. Tumasheva's article on the ethnic relations of Western Siberian Tatars, the ethnonyms qitay (qara qitay, qatay, qtay, kiden), telew (teli), joqsaba (toqsaba), and kangly are discussed, along with their relationships to anthroponyms (personal names) and toponyms (place names).

Famous Russian Turkologists such as N. Aristov, V.V. Radlov, V.V. Bartold, S.P. Tolstov, S.M. Abramzon, L.V. Gumilyov, D.Ye. Yeremeyev, N.A. Baskakov, L.V. Zuyev, A.N. Xanikov, B.A. Jdanko, and A.A. Valitov, among many others, have made significant contributions to the study of ethnonymy of Turkic peoples. Ethnonyms have also been specifically researched in kindred Turkic languages, including Uzbek, Kazakh, and Kyrgyz linguistics. For the study of Uzbek ethnonyms, historians like I.I. Umnyakov, K. Shoniyozov, B. Ahmedov, and A. Asqarov, as well as linguists such as X. Doniyorov, S. Qoraev, E. Begmatov, T. Nafasov, N. Oxunov, K. Marqae, and N. Begaliev, have conducted numerous researches. In Uzbek linguistics, ethnonymy is considered a less extensively researched area compared to toponymy and anthroponymy, with fewer dedicated research works. Notable publications in this field include K. Shoniyozov's "Towards an Ethnic History of the Uzbek People" [5] and "The formation process of the Uzbek people" [6], and B. Ahmedova's "The Uzbek ulus (nation)" [7].

In K. Shaniyazov's monograph, "On the Ethnic History of the Uzbek People", historical information about the Qipchaqs is provided, detailing their division into clans and tribes. In this work, the author categorizes the Kipchaks who lived in the Fergana Valley at the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th centuries into four groups: pure Kipchaks, Kyrgyz-Kipchaks, Qitay-Kipchaks, and Sart-Kipchaks. N. Begaliev's work, "From the History of Uzbek Ethnonyms" [8], includes a list of 92 Uzbek tribes [8:23-25], the Kungrad tribe and its tribal genealogy [8:51-56]. It also presents interesting information related to the etymology of several Turkic clan and tribal names.

Academics N.Ya. Mar, Czech scholar B. Grozny, and historians Sh. Aqinjanov, M. Xojan uli, D. Junisov, T. Januzaqov, and S. Jusip uli have all researched Kazakh ethnonyms. T. Januzaqov, in the "Ethnonymy" part of his work, "Sketch of Kazakh onomastics" [9], discussed ethnonymy and its connections with other sciences, ethnic terms, the linguistic and historical-ethnographic foundations of ethnonyms, and anthroponyms derived from ethnonyms. Duysen Junisov, a professor at I. Jansugirov Jetisu State University, in his article "Obsolete

Ethnonyms and Historical Features of the Language” [10], discussed other tribes and clans that coexisted with the Kazakh people during the period when Turkic-speaking peoples lived in a single social environment, as well as a number of obsolete ethnonyms related to them. Manasbay Xojan uli’s book, “Kazakh’s Ethnonym System” [11], published in Astana in 2011, provides extensive information on the Kazakh ethnonym system, based on historical, genealogical, and linguistic materials related to ethnonyms in the West Kazakhstan region.

The history of the Karakalpak people and their ethnogenetic issues began to be studied extensively, utilizing historical, archaeological, and ethnographic materials from the works of historians and specialists in related fields. On researching the history and ethnogenesis of the Karakalpak people, the works of prominent scholars such as P.P. Ivanov, S.P. Tolstov, T.A. Jdanko, S.E. Malov, N.A. Baskakov, S.K. Kamalov, D.S. Nasirov, V.N. Yagodin, L.S. Tolstova, and X. Esbergenov, along with Berdaq’s “Family tree” (Genealogy/Chronicle), have been of great importance. As a result of these scholars’ research, the ethnogenesis (origin) of the Karakalpak people is considerably clarified today.

A major achievement in recent Karakalpak historiography is the comprehensive work “Sketches of the history of the Karakalpak ASSR” [12], which summarizes the history of the Karakalpak people. This work was written by synthesizing extensive historical, archaeological, linguistic, anthropological, and folkloric materials covering the ancient, medieval, and modern history of the Karakalpak people. In T.A. Jdanko’s work, “Sketches of historical ethnography of the Karakalpaks” [13], maps illustrate the locations of Karakalpak tribes. It also includes a structural schema of clans and tribes, information about their tribe emblems and battle cries (slogans), and legends gathered from the people regarding their origins. This work features 11 maps, 16 tables, and concludes with a list of clan and tribal names.

L.S. Tolstova and A. Otemisov’s article, “Clarification of some issues of Karakalpak ethnogenesis” [14], explores historical legends collected from the Karakalpaks of the Takhtakopir district. The article details legends about the origin of the Karakalpaks’ MUYTEN tribe. The MUYTENS are divided into Aral MUYTENS and Zarafshan MUYTENS based on their settlement areas, and their division scheme is also presented. Additionally, an ethnographic map of the Takhtakopir district is included, showing the locations of the QOLDAULY, QOSTAMGALY, QARAMOYIN, IRGAQLY, TERISTAMGALY, MUYTEN, QITAY, and KIPSHAK tribes, along with the Kazakhs, using conventional symbols. L.S. Tolstova’s article, “The ethnographic group “MITAN” comprising Uzbeks of Samarkand

province” [15], provides materials collected on the Mitan (Muyten) ethnonym during an ethnographic expedition in Zarafshan in 1963. The article includes information about the Muytens living in the Ishrixon and Nurata districts (the latter now part of Navoiy region) of Samarkand province, as well as their occupations. It also maps the locations of Karakalpaks in Samarkand, including the Muytens. The ethnonym Moyten (Mitan, Moytan) can also be found in other works by L.S. Tolstova. Beyond these, other notable articles addressing ethnonym issues in the Karakalpak language include D. Aytmuratov’s “On the Turkic ethnonyms “Karakalpak”, black klobuks” [16] and “On the Origin of the Name “Karakalpak”” [17].

To date, discussions in Karakalpak linguistics concerning ethnonyms have primarily focused on their origin and etymology. However, the lexico-semantic features, morphological structure, relationship to word categories, and specific usage patterns of Karakalpak ethnonyms have not been thoroughly researched. A comprehensive study of Karakalpak ethnonyms and the creation of an ethnonymic dictionary are considered among the primary research objectives.

Studying ethnonyms from a linguistic perspective holds significant theoretical and practical importance. Each ethnonym carries a specific history, and their study allows for the acquisition of substantial information related to the history of a people and the history of a language. Ethnonyms in any given language consistently generate interest among its speakers, and even among other peoples.

References

1. Байраммырадов Г. Виды этнонимов и их семантика (на основе словарных данных) / Языка и культуры народов мира: Межкультурная коммуникация. – Москва: РУДН, 2019. С. 10-18.
2. Поляков А.С. К вопросу о содержании понятия «Этноним», xanderpolyakov@gmail.com
3. Никонов В.А. Этнонимия. – Москва: ГРВЛ. 1970.
4. Папов А.И. Названия народов СССР. – Ленинград: Наука, 1973.
5. Шаниязов К.Ш. К этнической истории узбекского народа (историко-этнографическое исследование на материалах кипчакского компонента). – Ташкент: Фан, 1974.
6. Шаниязов К.Ш. Ўзбек халқининг шаклланиш жараёни – Ташкент: шарқ, 2001.

7. Ahmedov B. O'zbek ulusi. —Toshkent: A Qodiriy. 1992.
8. Begaliev N. O'zbek etnonimlari tarixidan. – Samarqand: Samarqand davlat chet tillari instituti, 2005. B. 23-25.
9. Джанузаков Т. Очерк казахский ономастики – Алма-ата: Наука, 1982.
<https://anatili.kazgazeta.kz/news/19499 / 01.05.2014>
10. Манасбай Қожанұлы. Қазақ этнонимдер жүйесі. – Астана: 2011
11. Очерки истории Каракалпакской АССР. – Ташкент: Изд-во Академии наук Узбекской ССР, 1964.
12. Жданко Т.А. Очерки исторической этнографии Каракалпаков – Москва, Ленинград: 1960.
13. Толстова Л.С. Уточнение некоторых вопросов этногенеза Каракалпаков. – Нукус: Вестник Каракалпакского филиала АН Узбекистана, 1963, №4.
14. Толстова Л.С. Этнографический группа «митан» в составе узбеков Самаркандской области – Нукус: Вестник Каракалпакского филиала АН Узбекистана, 1963, №4.
15. Айтмуратов Д. О тюркских этнонимах «Каракалпак», черные клобуки – Нукус: Вестник Каракалпакского филиала АН Узбекистана, 1981, №2, С. 72-75.

